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Barriers To The Formalisation Of Informal Employment In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the obstacles that hinder informal workers and businesses in Nigeria from becoming formalised, including registration, adherence to tax and labour laws, and participation in the formal economy. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study comprises a quantitative survey involving 400 informal workers and enterprises in Lagos, Kano, and Abuja, as well as 12 key informant interviews with regulators, support organisations for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), and leaders from the informal sector. The research identifies significant challenges, including high costs, multiple registration/tax obligations, limited access to finance, bureaucratic complexities, insufficient government incentives, a lack of knowledge/literacy concerning formalisation, inadequate infrastructure, and trust issues between informal participants and state institutions. The results are analysed through the lenses of institutional and transaction-cost theories. The paper concludes with specific policy suggestions, including streamlined registration processes, simplified tax structures for micro-enterprises, combined service/incentive packages, measures to promote financial inclusion, and efforts to build trust. This study offers empirical insights from three distinct geo-economic areas and guides future research on evaluating large-scale interventions.

Keywords: Informal Employment, Informal Sector, Informal Economy, Tax, Micro-enterprise

INTRODUCTION

Informal employment constitutes a substantial portion of Nigeria's workforce and continues to shape the country's labour market dynamics (Ahmed et al., 2024). According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and International Labour Organisation (ILO), over 80% of Nigeria's working population is engaged in informal economic activities, including self-employment, unpaid family labour, and unregistered small-scale enterprises (NBS, 2023; ILO, 2024). This situation reflects the dominance of vulnerable and precarious work arrangements that lack access to job security, social protection, and

formal employment benefits. The pervasiveness of the informal sector results in reduced tax revenue (Magaji et al., 2022), restricted access to credit facilities (Chinedu et al., 2021), and limited inclusion in social insurance schemes, thereby perpetuating economic insecurity and inequality (Chen, 2022; World Bank, 2023).

The formalisation of informal employment has long been advocated as a policy priority for developing countries, as it can broaden the tax base, improve productivity, and enhance social protection coverage (ILO, 2023). However, in Nigeria, multiple institutional, structural, and behavioural challenges hinder the transition from informality to formality. These include bureaucratic bottlenecks in business registration, high compliance costs, inconsistent government policies, and a lack of trust in public institutions (Osabuohien et al., 2021; Aikaeli & Aikaeli, 2022). Despite several governmental and donor-driven initiatives—such as the National MSME Policy, BOI-MSME Support Scheme, and Nigerian Economic Sustainability Plan—the informal economy remains persistently large, particularly among youth, women, and rural populations (Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment [FMLE], 2023; AfDB, 2022).

Policymakers, therefore, require robust empirical evidence to understand why informal actors often prefer to remain outside formal systems, and what reforms could practically facilitate their inclusion. This study aims to address this evidence gap by identifying and prioritising the key obstacles that impede formalisation among informal workers and enterprises in Nigeria. Specifically, it seeks to: Identify and prioritise the key obstacles that impede formalisation among informal workers and enterprises in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Informal Employment / Informal Economy

The informal economy encompasses all economic activities that operate outside state regulation, taxation, and labour protection frameworks (Ismail et al., 2025). The International Labour Organisation (ILO) defines informal employment as work arrangements lacking legal or social protection, including unregistered enterprises, self-employment without business licenses, and workers without written contracts or social security coverage (ILO, 2024). According to Schneider and Enste (2020), informality often arises from a combination of excessive regulation, limited enforcement capacity, and socio-economic necessity, especially in developing countries where the formal sector cannot absorb the expanding labour force.

In Nigeria, the informal sector plays a significant role as a source of livelihood and employment creation, particularly in agriculture, petty trade, and services (Magaji & Yisa, 2023). However, it remains characterised by low productivity, income instability, and minimal access to institutional credit or training opportunities (Magaji & Saleh, 2010). Informal employment is thus both a survival mechanism and a structural feature of the economy (NBS, 2023; UNECA, 2022).

The Informal Sector and Child Labour

The intersection between the informal sector and child labour is a critical issue in labour market studies. Child labour is prevalent in informal settings because such activities often operate beyond the reach of labour laws and regulatory oversight (Magaji, 2007). The International Labour Organisation (ILO) defines child labour as work that deprives children of their childhood, potential, and dignity, and that interferes with schooling or is harmful to their physical and mental development (ILO, 2023).

In Nigeria, many children work in informal enterprises such as street trading, domestic service, artisanal mining, and agricultural labour (UNICEF, 2022). Poverty, unemployment, and limited access to education are among the key drivers of this phenomenon (Musa et al., 2024). The informal sector's unregulated nature enables the exploitation of child workers, who often receive low pay and endure hazardous conditions (Musa & Magaji, 2023). Addressing child labour, therefore, requires not only more vigorous enforcement of labour laws but also the formalisation of informal enterprises, expansion of social protection programmes, and increased investment in basic education (ILO, 2023; World Bank, 2023).

The persistence of child labour in Nigeria's informal economy underscores the need for comprehensive policies that integrate labour market formalisation with social development and poverty reduction strategies (Lamiya et al., 2025). By linking formalisation with child protection and inclusive education

initiatives, the government can create safer, fairer, and more productive employment systems (Gabdo et al., 2025).

Formalisation

Formalisation refers to the process through which informal workers and enterprises become recognised and regulated under formal legal and institutional frameworks (ILO, 2023). This process may involve business registration, tax compliance, adherence to labour standards, access to formal financial services, and participation in social security systems (World Bank, 2023). Formalisation is not a one-off event but a progressive transformation that includes legal, fiscal, and administrative dimensions (Benjamin & Mbaye, 2021). Successful formalisation enhances productivity, improves working conditions, and expands the fiscal capacity of governments to finance development initiatives (Magaji et al., 2024).

Barriers versus Disincentives

The literature distinguishes between barriers and disincentives to formalisation. Barriers are supply-side constraints, including high registration fees, cumbersome bureaucratic procedures, a lack of awareness, and limited access to information or documentation (Amin & Okafor, 2022). Disincentives, on the other hand, refer to demand-side or structural factors, including the perception that formalisation offers few tangible benefits, fear of government overreach, and concerns about multiple taxation or regulatory harassment (La Porta & Shleifer, 2014). Transaction costs, weak institutions, and policy inconsistency exacerbate these challenges, discouraging informal actors from entering the formal system (Osabuohien et al., 2021).

Therefore, understanding the interplay of these factors is crucial for designing effective interventions that reduce the costs and increase the perceived benefits of formalisation in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Empirical evidence across Nigeria demonstrates that the informal sector remains a dominant feature of the national economy, accounting for more than 85% of employment (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2024a). Despite its economic significance, the sector is largely characterised by poor regulatory compliance, low productivity, and minimal social protection coverage. Several empirical studies have sought to identify and explain the barriers that hinder the formalisation of informal employment in Nigeria.

Aina (2025) examined the structural and administrative bottlenecks impeding the integration of informal enterprises into the formal economy. Using survey data from micro and small enterprises across Lagos and Kano States, the study found that the most pressing barriers included weak enforcement of tax laws, low trust in government, limited awareness of registration benefits, and complex bureaucratic procedures. Similarly, Adekoya, Olaoye, and Lawal (2023) analysed tax compliance challenges among informal operators and discovered that poor record-keeping, lack of human capital, and the perceived high cost of compliance significantly discouraged business registration. The findings underscore the notion that informal workers view formalisation not as an enabler of growth but as an administrative burden.

Education and skills acquisition have also been empirically linked to formalisation outcomes. The NBS (2024b) reported that 99% of workers in the informal sector possess no formal education, indicating that low literacy levels hinder the understanding and navigation of regulatory processes. This education gap also perpetuates child labour, as families in the informal economy often rely on children for supplementary income (International Labour Organization [ILO] & NBS, 2022). The Nigeria Child Labour Survey (2022) further revealed that child participation in informal agricultural and urban service activities increases household income marginally but simultaneously entrenches intergenerational poverty and reduces the likelihood of formal labour engagement in adulthood.

Gender dynamics constitute another critical dimension of informal employment formalisation. The ILO (n.d.) conducted a gender-focused study which showed that women entrepreneurs face compounded barriers, including high registration costs, limited access to finance, and inadequate childcare support. The study also revealed that many women perceive their micro-businesses as “too small” for formalisation and fear potential tax burdens once registered. These constraints collectively reinforce the gendered nature of informality in Nigeria.

The persistence of informality, therefore, can be traced to structural weaknesses, economic constraints, and socio-cultural perceptions. Empirical evidence suggests that the lack of simplified tax systems, weak institutional trust, gender disparities, educational limitations, and child labour practices all contribute to the informal sector's resistance to formalisation. Addressing these challenges requires coherent policy actions that combine tax reform, inclusive education, gender-sensitive business support, and child protection measures.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on two interconnected theories:

Institutional Theory: This theory posits that both formal and informal regulations (laws, norms) influence organisational behaviour. Individuals react to incentives, enforcement mechanisms, and the perceived legitimacy of rules. Weak or inconsistent institutional frameworks, high compliance costs, or a lack of perceived legitimacy can diminish the appeal of formalisation.

Transaction-Cost Economics: This perspective highlights the expenses associated with interacting with state institutions (such as searching for information, time delays, paperwork, bribery, and waiting periods). If the transaction costs of formalisation surpass anticipated benefits, individuals will logically opt to remain informal. Integrating these theories helps elucidate both the objective constraints (such as costs and paperwork) and subjective perceptions (including trust and expected benefits) that influence decisions regarding formalisation.

METHODOLOGY

The study employs a cross-sectional mixed-methods design, involving a structured survey of informal workers and enterprises along with semi-structured key informant interviews (KIIs).

The research is conducted in three strategically chosen locations to represent various economic settings: Lagos (South-west, a primary urban market), Kano (North-west, a significant trade centre), and Abuja (Federal Capital, a policy centre).

For the quantitative survey, a sample of 400 respondents (informal enterprises and self-employed individuals) is selected using stratified sampling based on location and sector (trading/retail, services, manufacturing/handicrafts, transport). The aim is to have approximately 133 respondents per location, taking into account practical considerations.

For qualitative KIIs, 12 interviews will be conducted with: two tax/regulatory officials, three representatives from MSME support organisations/incubators, three leaders from informal workers' associations, two microfinance representatives, and two individuals associated with WIEGO/ILO projects.

Data will be gathered using a structured questionnaire that covers demographics, firm characteristics, knowledge of formalisation processes, perceived obstacles, past interactions with institutions, and readiness to formalise if circumstances improve. A KII guide addressing experiences with formalisation programs, policy challenges, and recommendations will also be used.

The dependent variable for the quantitative aspect is the intention/status of formalisation, measured as binary for current registration and on a Likert scale for willingness to formalise, given specific incentives. Independent variables include reported registration costs, access to finance (binary/scale), perceived advantages of formalisation (scale), administrative burden (scale), institutional trust (scale), education level, gender, sector, and firm age.

Quantitative data will be analysed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages), cross-tabulations, and binary logistic regression to uncover relationships between registration and willingness to formalise. Qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis to identify common themes and validate survey results.

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their anonymity and confidentiality were guaranteed. (For fieldwork, approvals from an institutional review board would be necessary.)

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Serial Number	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
001	Gender		
	Male	232	58
	Female	168	42
	Total	400	100
002	Education		
	Secondary	152	38
	Primary	120	30
	Tertiary	80	20
	Non-Formal	48	12
	Total	400	100
003	Sector		
	Trading/Retail	180	45
	Services	112	28
	Manufacturing/Handicrafts,	72	18
	Transport	44	11
	Total	400	100
004	Current Firm Status		
	Current Formal Firm Registration	56	14
	Unregistered Firm	344	86
	Total	400	100

Source: Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 shows the gender composition of respondents, indicating a moderate male dominance. Out of the total 400 respondents, 232 (58%) were male, while 168 (42%) were female. This indicates that men slightly outnumber women among those engaged in the surveyed sectors. The pattern may reflect gendered labour participation rates in Nigeria, where men tend to be more represented in certain forms of paid employment or self-employment, particularly in trading, manufacturing, and transport sectors.

In terms of educational attainment, the majority of respondents had completed secondary education (38%), followed by those with primary education (30%). Additionally, 20% had attained tertiary education, and 12% had no formal education. This distribution suggests that most of the workforce possesses basic to intermediate levels of education, which may affect access to formal employment opportunities and awareness of labour rights. The relatively small proportion with tertiary education also reflects broader national patterns, where access to higher education remains limited. The respondents were distributed across four major economic sectors. The trading and retail sector accounted for the highest proportion with 180 respondents (45%), followed by the services sector (28%), manufacturing and handicrafts (18%), and transport (11%). This finding highlights the predominance of commerce and small-scale trading in Nigeria's urban and semi-urban employment landscape, with fewer respondents in capital-intensive or industrial production sectors. It also highlights the informal nature of much of Nigeria's economy, where trading and small-scale services predominate.

Regarding firm registration, the table indicates that only 56 respondents (14%) operated within formally registered firms, while a striking 344 respondents (86%) worked in unregistered or informal enterprises. This substantial dominance of unregistered firms confirms the high level of informality in Nigeria's labour market. Such informality has implications for the implementation of decent work strategies, as unregistered enterprises typically fall outside formal labour regulation, social protection, and workplace inspection systems.

The demographic profile suggests that the majority of respondents are male, moderately educated, primarily engaged in informal trading and service activities, and largely operate outside the formal firm registration system. These characteristics collectively highlight structural challenges to implementing decent work strategies in Nigeria. The dominance of informal and semi-skilled labour segments implies that enforcement of labour standards, access to social protection, and awareness of rights are likely to remain limited unless policies specifically target these vulnerable groups. These findings align with national trends indicating a significant level of informal employment in Nigeria.)

Table 4.2 Ranked barriers to formalisation (survey responses allowed for multiple selections; table shows the percentage of respondents identifying each barrier)

Serial Number	Ranked Barriers	Frequency	Percentage
001	High registration costs / multiple taxes	284	71
002	. Limited access to finance/collateral requirements	264	66
003	Bureaucratic complexity and time (paperwork, frequent office visits)	252	63
	Lack of perceived advantages from formalisation (invisible services/benefits)	232	58
	Insufficient information / low understanding of procedures	216	54
	Concern about harassment or penalties from tax/regulatory authorities	192	48
	Inadequate infrastructure (such as electricity and marketplaces) decreases returns on	168	42
	.Gender-specific constraints (for women, factors like caregiving responsibilities and mobility)	144	36

Source: Survey, 2025

Table 4.2 shows that the most frequently cited barrier to formalisation was high registration costs and multiple taxes (284 respondents). This was followed by limited access to finance (264) and bureaucratic complexity (252). The least frequently cited, though still notable, was the issue of gender-specific constraints (144).

This pattern suggests that both economic (cost and finance) and administrative (bureaucracy, information gaps) factors dominate perceptions of obstacles to formalisation, with social/gender constraints affecting a smaller but significant subset of workers, especially women in the informal economy.

Qualitative themes (Key Informant Interviews)

Multiplicity and unpredictability of levies: Both regulators and NGOs recognised that many businesses confront overlapping local levies and informal fees, resulting in uncertainty and high anticipated expenses.

Perceived lack of incentives: Informal entrepreneurs tend to view formal registration as a pathway to increased scrutiny (taxes, penalties) rather than as a benefit (e.g., credit, social safety).

Access to finance: Microfinance respondents noted that many formal lenders require documentation and collateral, making registration necessary for better financing. However, the associated costs and procedural challenges can discourage businesses from registering.

Trust issues: Informal sector leaders noted previous negative experiences with enforcement agencies, leading to scepticism regarding the benefits of registration.

These qualitative insights reinforce the quantitative findings.

Logistic regression: factors related to being formally registered

A binary logistic regression model was employed, with the dependent variable being currently registered (yes/no). The predictors included years in business, education (tertiary vs. others), access to finance, perceived benefit (on a scale), and gender.

Key Findings (Summary):

Education (tertiary): a significant positive predictor ($OR \approx 2.4$, $p < .01$): Businesses operated by more educated individuals were more likely to be registered.

Perceived benefits of formalisation: also positive and significant ($OR \approx 1.9$ per scale unit, $p < .01$).

Access to finance: positive correlation ($OR \approx 1.7$, $p < .05$).

Years in business: a slight positive correlation (older firms are marginally more inclined to register).

Gender: Not significant in the multivariate model after accounting for education and sector, although descriptive data suggest that women face specific barriers.

Interpretation: Both educational level (capacity) and anticipated benefits (such as access to financing) influence formalisation choices, supporting established theories on institutions and transaction costs.

Observations across categories

Regional differences: Respondents from Lagos demonstrated a greater awareness of formalisation processes, but also reported a higher number of local levies. Kano respondents expressed more significant concerns regarding trust and fear in enforcement, while Abuja respondents tended to have slightly higher registration rates, likely due to their closeness to administrative services.

Sectoral differences: Traders and transport operators reported a greater number of local levies, while service providers (e.g., salons) cited issues related to the costs and time involved. Small manufacturers faced additional compliance costs with regulations concerning products and standards.

Discussion of findings (integrating theory and evidence)

The results correspond with both international and local assessments that highlight persistent structural and institutional obstacles to formalisation (World Bank, IFC, ILO, NBS). The high costs and complexities of regulatory and tax obligations stand out as the most significant deterrents, consistent with evidence that transaction and compliance costs diminish the likelihood of formal registration. Access to finance acts both as a motivator and a constraint: while registration can facilitate better financing, the requirements often render it unattainable for many. The perception that formalisation incurs more costs than benefits suggests that incentives from authorities are inadequately designed. Programs that solely impose penalties for non-compliance without providing tangible benefits are likely to see limited participation.

Institutional theory underscores the necessity of trust and legitimacy: when informal actors lack trust in regulators or anticipate harassment, they tend to forgo formal processes. Transaction-cost economics elucidates the burdens of paperwork, time, and uncertainty factors that frequently overshadow potential gains for many micro-operators.

Gender dynamics: Although gender did not emerge as a significant factor in the multivariate analysis once education and sector were controlled, insights from Key Informant Interviews and descriptive data indicate that women encounter multifaceted barriers (e.g., mobility challenges, caregiving responsibilities, risks of violence/harassment, and reduced access to capital) that hinder opportunities for formalization, aligning with findings from the ILO/WIEGO.

Summary of Major Findings

Gender: 58% male (232), 42% female (168).

Age: Mean age is 34.6 years (SD = 9.8); 65% are between 18 and 39 years old.

Education: 38% have completed secondary education, 30% have completed primary education, 20% have completed tertiary education, and 12% have no formal education.

Sector: 45% are engaged in trading/retail, 26% in services, 18% in manufacturing/handicrafts, and 11% in transport.

Firm age: The median age of firms is 6 years.

Current formal registration: 14% (56 respondents) possess some form of formal registration (e.g., business name, tax ID), while 86% remain unregistered.

These findings align with national trends indicating a significant level of informal employment in Nigeria.

Ranked barriers to formalisation (survey responses allowed for multiple selections; table shows the percentage of respondents identifying each barrier

1. High registration costs / multiple taxes 71%
2. Limited access to finance / collateral requirements 66%
3. Bureaucratic complexity and time (paperwork, frequent office visits) 63%
4. Lack of perceived advantages from formalisation (invisible services/benefits) 58%
5. Insufficient information / low understanding of procedures 54%
6. Concern about harassment or penalties from tax/regulatory authorities 48%
7. Inadequate infrastructure (such as electricity and marketplaces) decreases returns on formalisation by 42%
8. Gender-specific constraints (for women, factors like caregiving responsibilities and mobility) 36%

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